

INCULCATING VALUE SYSTEM IN STUDENTS

Dr. Mahabir Singh,

Assistant Professor,

K. M. College of Education, Bhiwani.

Ms. Amritpal Kaur,

Assistant Professor,

IETVE, Panjab University,

Chandigarh.

Abstract

Due to modernization the values are declining day by day. Education is meant for enhancing the values among the masses but the realm of education is that the educational institutions are not fulfilling their duties. The teacher is meant for the proper growth of the students. In the modern world there is no harmony between the outer life of action and the inner life emotions. We also find that there is a crisis of character owing to deterioration of values in social, economic, cultural, moral and religious spheres of man.

Education is a powerful instrument that develops the desired and undesired values in the youth. Even though the main focus of education system is to inculcate many more values such as moral values, spiritual values, economic values, social values, health values, recreational values, aesthetic values etc., due to materialistic (increasing conflicts in life) prominence among the masses that the spiritual values. So it the need of the hour that we should join hands to develop the values.

Key words: *Inculcation, Value, System and Students*

Introduction

“Educating for character is a moral imperative if we care about the future of our society and our children.”

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Human values are closely integrated with human life. They are intertwined with our day to day chores. No human life is possible without values. Yes every living human being lives by certain values. It is only the proportion and combination of negative and positive values which separates a noble human being from a not so noble human being. The positive values are Honesty, Compassion, Integrity, Forgiveness, Love, Knowledge, Discipline, Faith, and Leadership. The negative values like prejudice, hatred, greed, selfishness, and others need not be discussed here. Every human being is born neutral and is like a black slate and no mindset. How much of virtues and vices are filled in depends solely on the parents, teachers, circumstances, environment, and sometimes even geographic location.

However, everyone can be inculcated with human values by the parents, teachers, friends, well wishers and even strangers. Especially Teachers can help students to differentiate between right and wrong and make them understand the importance of imbibing moral and ethical values. Self education of human values is also possible by meeting, learning, and reading about, great individuals living a holistic life.

This article includes a video which consists of highly enlightened conversation between two highly respected human beings and noble laureates. Which is also a good source of learning and inculcating human values?

Meaning of Value

A value may be defined in terms of having worth or of being valuable. In this sense we can say that goodness and beauty are values where as evil and ugliness would be disvalues.

Values are standards or principles considered important in life.

Coming from with in	Being practiced
Love	Punctuation
Kindness	Discipline
Compassion	Obedience
Mercy	Behaviour
Sympathy	Character

From the philosophical point of view value signifies neither a thing nor individual, but thought or point of view. Anything, which is useful to a person, becomes valuable to him. This particular thing may not be useful to another person. Hence, it is of no value to him. Thus from the Philosophical point of view, value is directly related to what one believes in or thinks.

Anything or everything which is good, useful, important, significant and valuable from educational point of view and has a bearing on education is "Educational value".

From Sociological point of view, social values are cultural standards that indicate the general goods deemed desirable for an organized society. What is right and important for society is sociological value. This value refers to social arrangements and social behavior and an individual is dealing with, or capable of distinguishing between, right and wrong.

Values are socially approved drives and goals that are internalized through the process of conditioning, learning or socialization and that becomes subjective preferences, standards and aspirations, said **R. K. Mukherjee**

In the most elementary sense, value means what is actually liked, prized, esteemed, desired, approved or enjoyed at any time. It is the actual experience of enjoying a desired object or activity, **Edgar Brightman** said.

Why Values?

- Values bring Quality and meaning of life.
- Values give a person his identity and character.
- Values act as guidelines they tell him what he should and should not do.
- They make us realize that –what we all more important than what we have.

Adopting a moral development perspective believe that moral thinking develops in stages through a specific sequence. This approach is based primarily on the work of Lawrence Kohlberg (1969, 1984) as presented in his 6 stages and 25 "basic moral concepts." This approach focuses primarily on moral values, such as fairness, justice, equity, and human dignity; other types of values (social, personal, and aesthetic) are usually not considered. It is assumed that students invariably progress developmentally in their thinking about moral issues. They can comprehend one stage above their current primary stage and exposure to the next higher level is essential for enhancing moral development. Educators attempt to stimulate students to develop more complex moral reasoning patterns through the sequential stages.

Kohlberg's view of human nature is similar to that presented in the ideas of other developmental psychologists such as Piaget (1932, 1962), Erikson (1950), and Loevinger et al. (1970). This perspective views the person as an active initiator and a reactor within the context of his or her environment; the individual cannot fully change the environment, but neither can the environment fully mold the individual. A person's actions are the result of his or her feelings, thoughts, behaviors, and experiences. Although the environment can determine the content of one's experiences, it cannot determine its form. Genetic structures already inside the person are primarily responsible for the way in which a person internalizes the content, and organizes and transforms it into personally meaningful data.

LAWRENCE KOHLBERG'S STAGES OF MORAL DEVELOPMENT

LEVEL	STAGE	SOCIAL ORIENTATION
Pre-conventional	1	Obedience and Punishment
	2	Individualism, Instrumentalism, and Exchange
Conventional	3	"Good boy/girl"
	4	Law and Order
Post-conventional	5	Social Contract
	6	Principled Conscience

Inculcating value system in students:

Most educators viewing values education from the perspective of inculcation see values as socially or culturally accepted standards or rules of behavior. Valuing is therefore considered a process of the student identifying with and accepting the standards or norms of the important individuals and institutions within his society. The student "incorporates" these values into his or her own value system. These educators take a view of human nature in which the individual is treated, during the inculcation process, as a reactor rather than as an initiator. Extreme advocates such as Talcott Parsons (1951) believe that the needs and goals of society should transcend and even define the needs and goals of the individuals.

Due to liberalization, industrialization and globalization rapid changes are occurring in almost all social sciences. It is not a one man's job, we can help each other to inculcate the values in the students. The value possessed and their attitudes according to the changes should be known up to date vast changes are occurring in the education. So called philosophical foundations of India are declining day to day with the country in a state of social turbulence, the

goals and functions of formal education need to be reassessed and updated. Through value based education we can change the world.

However, advocates who consider an individual to be a free, self-fulfilling participant in society tend to inculcate values as well, especially values such as freedom to learn, human dignity, justice, and self-exploration. Both the social- and individualistic-oriented advocates would argue the notion that certain values are universal and absolute. The source of these values is open to debate. On the one hand some advocates argue they derive from the natural order of the universe; others believe that values originate in an omnipotent Creator.

1. Submit yourself to a guru:

Your guru should be a person, whom you trust completely, & in whom you can confide confidently. The trust between the teacher and taught should be strictly mutual and of highest order.

2. Keep your life simple and honest.

Honesty is not a policy or business transaction. It is the most natural and profitable way of leading life. And it is not as difficult as it is made out to be. Start with an understanding that Honesty is a value and not an attribute. Each value has a denominator. Fix your denominator for this value. Start with the conviction that no one is either 100% or 0% honest. Grid yourself: somewhere in between the extremes. Start being less dishonest every day and slowly graduate to being more honest every day. If you feel that you are more honest today than you were yesterday move yourself up the grid a little. Be very conservative and mean while grading you. Let your physical being work hard and deliver definitive measurable results to convince your inner being. Don't be charitable to yourself, but celebrate small success. This will encourage and motivate you to raise the bar daily and perhaps even many times in a day.

3. Be compassionate.

Not every human being is as empowered or as privileged as you may be, people with lesser attributes or lesser privileges are not lesser human beings. They may be

children of lesser gods or victims of circumstances. Show compassion, treat them as your equals, and try in your own way to elevate them physically, mentally and spiritually.

4. Treat Integrity as the most essential part of your life:

Integrity comes out of ownership. Take ownership of your responsibilities both at home and the work place. Loss of integrity means loss of character. And loss of character means loss of your life mentally and spiritually. There is no use being only physical alive.

5. Criticize and reprimand the act not the actor.

Forgiveness is not only a virtue, but also an act that creates remorse & makes a better person of the person forgiven. It also wins you a friend.

6. Love thy neighbor and everyone else's too if possible:

Spread love large heartedly. Spare no one human beings, animals, nature and innate things. Reciprocation will start sooner or later from all living things and ultimately you will end up winning hearts.

7. Upgrade your knowledge continuously.

The most knowledgeable also seeks knowledge to become more knowledgeable. Pursuit of knowledge should be a continuous process. Knowledge can not only be acquired from books, teacher, institutions, but also from things around us including nature.

8. Be disciplined in your thoughts and actions.

Having time sense is just one part of the discipline. Discipline encompasses every aspect of your day to day life. Your actions, your attire, your speech, your silence, your movements, your treatment of others and yourself. Don't be undisciplined even to yourself.

9. Practice yoga first thing in the morning:

After completing morning chores, it is essential to start with yoga. Perform some easy asana as per your endurance power and availability of time preferably in an open space (rooftop, lawns, or a large room with lot of ventilation). These help in the circulation of blood and fresh air to the various cells, tissues, organs and systems of the

human body. A healthy body is a good generator of healthy thoughts and inculcation of values becomes that much easier.

Some fostering techniques are used by the teacher to inculcate the values in the students

The school as a whole should Foster caring beyond the classroom and create a positive moral culture in the school by:

- By giving a place for moral values in the curriculum. By introducing a course on moral values as a part of all levels primary, Secondary, Master Degree and higher level also.
- Moral values can be explained through stories, illustrations, poetry and novel we can inculcate moral values in the students.
- In order to develop the values among the students the school should organize excursion to places of cultural, religious and historical importance. We can develop a feeling of love for cultural heritage.
- The teacher can organize regional/state/national level competitions and encourage the students for participate in the competitions and co-operative group work.
- Educate students through posters, advertisements and dramatizations; those are all a part in the curriculum.
- Giving course training to students to develop moral values in the society (to educate the special children, illiteracy programme, Health and Hygiene Social Mobilization, N.S.S., N.C.C. Scout and Guide etc.)
- The teacher can organize personality development programme.
- The teacher should be the living embodiment of all the human values.
- The institution can organize extension lectures on morality or value education.
- The institution can arrange an exhibition of value added literature.

John F. Kennedy has rightly said that, "How are we going to get the best education in the world? One of the ways is to have the best trained teachers."

Conclusion:

Value development in children is like growing a plant. In this process, the society, parents, public servants, textbooks, media, and teachers play their respective roles. Among various entities, the teacher becomes the facilitator to ensure that the value development takes place as per norms. Value education helps in developing character, good conduct, moral integrity, self discipline, compassion, love for all living beings, responsibility and many other positive qualities in students. It makes them feel better about themselves. The teacher should always play a proactive role in cultivating the minds of children and developing strong values in them. Unless efforts and struggle is made the results cannot be seen. So let us as teachers lean to act and not to preach alone.

REFERENCES:

- Bhati, Mahabir Singh et. al. (2010). Value Inculcation in Teacher Education, paper presented in National Seminar at Bhagwan Mahavir College of Education, Jagdishpur, Sonapat, Haryana.
- Kohlberg, L. (1969). Stage and sequence: The cognitive developmental approach to socialization. In D. Goslin (Ed.), *Handbook of socialization theory and research*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- Kohlberg, L. (1984). *The psychology of moral development*. San Francisco: Harper & Row.
- Mathur, S. S. (2007) Educational Psychology, Vinod Pustak Mandir: Agra, pp. 110-111
- Sachdeva, M. S. et. al, Philosophical and Sociological bases of education, Bharat Book Centre, Ludhiana, 2001-02
- Values retrieved from www.edpsycinteractive.org/topics/affect/values.html
- Venkataiah, N. et. al, Research in value education, A.P.H. Publishing Corporation, New Delhi
- Yadav and Yadav, Education in the Emerging Indian Society, Tandon Publication, Ludhiana